

Bell's Theorem might provide support to a Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe

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Abstract

The Classic Physics and the Quantum Physics are two branches of the nowadays Science of Physics, which are still incompatible.

Einstein's Relativity theories, which are the leading acceptable theories of the nowadays Classic Physics, present the Universe as a "Block Universe", in which Time is not a flow of events, where the past vanishes and does not exist anymore, and the future is not yet created. Instead, the "Block Universe" model presents that the past, present and future are all equally real and coexist tenselessly, and everything, the past, present and future are all predefined and engraved in that "Block Universe" model of the Universe.

On the other hand, the Quantum Mechanics presents, that the future is created continuously when particles interact with the environment, and the state of each particle is presented by what the Quantum Mechanics denotes as the "Wave Function" which presents the probabilities to find the particle in various locations, such that, before the particle is measured, or interacts with the environment, it can actually be in all those locations at once, and only after the particle is measured, or interacts with the environment, the "Wave Function Collapses" and the particle "chooses" *randomly*, to be only in one specific location.

Actually, that "Wave Function Collapse" is one of the most mysterious phenomena in Physics.

But it seems that Bell's Theorem, and the experiments that followed it, settled that long debate about it, providing the means to establish that the Quantum Mechanics view on this matter is the correct view and the Classic Physics and Einstein's Relativity theories view on this matter is not correct.

Bell's Inequality provided the logic and the mathematics behind this decision, and physicists such as Alain Aspect, John Clauser and Anton Zeilinger, who also won the Nobel prize on that, provided the experimental justification.

However, although the above debate was settled, there is also still a need, to understand more precisely, what actually happens in experiments relating to Quantum entangled particles, which is what was tested in Alain Aspect, John Clauser and Anton Zeilinger experiments.

The author of this paper refers to additional papers, by the author of this paper, which present significant and reasonable arguments, which argue that the nowadays branch of the Classic Physics might be misleading in how it presents the concept of the Space-Time.

These additional papers propose to replace the Einstein's "Block Universe" model of the Universe with an alternate model, of a Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe, in which, each Energy might embed its own private Space-Time facet, or attribute, such that each such Space-Time cannot be considered to be a real entity, that really exists in the Universe.

And this paper argues, that Bell's Theorem, and the experiments that followed it, might be also used to support the above-mentioned Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe, and this might also fill in the above-mentioned gap, which might be the need, to understand more precisely, what actually happens in experiments relating to Quantum entangled particles, which is what was tested in Alain Aspect, John Clauser and Anton Zeilinger experiments.

In addition to the above, the above-mentioned additional papers, also propose additional experiments, based *only* on the Classic Physics, which if implemented successfully, might provide *additional validity* to the proposed Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe.

The support that might be provided to the proposed model, of a Multi-Space-Times of the Universe, by the Bell's Theorem, and the experiments that followed it, is still based on the Quantum Mechanics.

Thus, because these additional experiments, proposed in the above-mentioned additional papers, are based *only* on the Classic Physics, this might also provide a lead for further narrowing the gap between the Classic Physics and the Quantum Physics.

Thus, an implementation of the above-mentioned experiments, or any other experiments that might provide validity to the proposed Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe, as presented in the above-mentioned papers, should be an important and a significant endeavor.

1. Elaborations on Bell's Theorem versus Einstein's Relativity theories

Bell's Theorem (1) is one of the most significant discoveries in Physics. It proves mathematically and experimentally that our Existence cannot be local and realistic.

In other words, it proves that Einstein's Relativity theories are not completely correct, and the probabilistic nature of the Quantum Mechanics is not an illusion.

In the nowadays Science of Classic Physics, Einstein's Relativity theories are the leading acceptable theories of the Classic Physics.

Einstein's four-dimensional Interwoven Space-Time concept, which Einstein's General Relativity theory (GRT) (2) assumes that it is a *real, existing* entity in the Existence, is the foundational backbone of the two most successful and experimentally verified theories in the mainstream Classic Physics: Special Relativity Theory (SRT) (3) and General Relativity Theory (GRT) (2).

The standard confirmed view, which is the established, tested and practical realm of the current mainstream Classic Physics, is that the Universe, or the Existence, embeds a *single* four-dimensional Interwoven Space-Time manifold, which consists of three spatial dimensions (x, y, z) and one temporal dimension (t), unified into a *single* geometric Entity.

That model accurately predicts and describes Gravity, the orbits of planets, the bending of Light around massive bodies, time-dilation, and the propagation of Gravitational Waves, all of which have been experimentally confirmed.

Thus, for all practical macroscopic phenomena, and for the vast majority of Physics (including the Standard Model of Particle Physics which operates on this background), the Universe, or the Existence, is treated as a *single* four-dimensional Space-Time with a *single* geometry.

However, the nowadays Science of Physics still embeds unresolved Paradoxes, incompatibilities between various branches of Physics, and Einstein's Relativity theories also rendered the Human's perception of the Free Choice as an illusion, misleading perception.

And as also presented already above, Bell's Theorem provided the logic and the mathematics, and the experiments that followed it provided the experimental proof, that our Existence cannot be local and realistic, which, in other words, it proves that Einstein's Relativity theories are not completely correct, and the probabilistic nature of the Quantum Mechanics is not an illusion.

The Quantum Physics challenges the rigid determinism implied by Einstein's "Block Universe" (4) model of the Universe, via one of the most mysterious phenomena in Physics, the Wave Function Collapse.

While Einstein's "Block Universe" model presents a constant, predetermined future, the Quantum Mechanics presents a Universe in which the future is not established until a measurement is performed.

In the Quantum Mechanics Universe particles do not exist in one specific location before they are measured. Instead, they are in a superposition state, in a cloud of probabilities in which a particle might be in all possible locations at once.

The mathematics that describes this cloud is denoted as the "Wave Function", which represents the probability to find the particle at a certain location, and when a measurement is performed on the particle, or the particle interacts with the environment, the Wave Function Collapses *immediately*, and the particle "chooses" *randomly* a specific location in the reality.

In the above description, the element that actually breaks Einstein's "Block Universe" determinism is a pure randomness or an indeterminism.

According to the Copenhagen interpretation (5) of the Quantum Physics, the particle's "election" where to appear when the Wave Function collapses, is not dictated by "hidden laws" or an early planning, it is purely *random*.

Einstein didn't like this, according to his allegedly famous saying: "God does not play dice".

If the future already exists and engraved in Einstein's four-dimensional Block, as Einstein believed, then, the result of the measurement was already engraved there, which should imply that no real probability collapse occurred. Instead, Einstein proposed that only an illusion of a random collapse occurred, because we don't have enough knowledge to understand what really happened.

In 1935, Einstein, Podolsky and Rosen published a thought experiment (6) about the Quantum Entanglement phenomenon.

The experiments relating to the Quantum Entanglement phenomenon manifest that, if two particles are entangled, a measurement of one particle *immediately* determines the state of the other particle, even if the distance between them is huge.

Einstein argued that this "instant communication" is impossible. He called it "spooky action at a distance". Einstein argued that particles might have "hidden variables" which might explain these results such that the model of a deterministic "Block Universe" can still prevail. Details of these Einstein's arguments can be found in the above-mentioned reference (6).

However, about 30 years later, in 1964, John Bell formulated his famous Inequality which states the following: If the Universe is indeed deterministic and local, as the Einstein's "Block Universe" presents, then, the correlation between the measurements results of two entangled particles cannot exceed a certain threshold, if these particles are measured extensively over a wide range of changing angles. If the measurements will exceed this threshold, then, Einstein's assumption of "hidden variables" is wrong. Details on Bell's Inequality can be found in the above-mentioned reference about Bell's Inequality (1).

Then, physicists such as Alain Aspect, John Clauser and Anton Zeilinger (7) created entangled photons, separated them apart, over long distances, and measured their properties extensively over a wide range of changing angles. Their result showed that Bell's inequality was violated again and again, which implied that the Quantum Mechanics approach was correct and not Einstein's approach.

Thus, Einstein refused to accept the idea that the collapse of the Wave Function, presented by the Quantum Mechanics is completely random because Einstein believed in Local Realism, which states that particles have constant and defined features (such as location or spin), also if we do not measure them, which implies Realism, and no influence or data can propagate faster than the velocity of Light, which implies Locality.

However, modern Quantum Physics proves again and again that this random collapse is real.

Bell's theorem and the experiments that followed it actually state that the Universe is not Realistic and particles do not have constants and defined features before we measure them, because the future is not predefined into a "Block Universe" as Einstein's General Relativity theory (GRT) (2)

implies. Instead, the collapse of the Wave Function, presented by the Quantum Mechanics, is a real creative event in the Universe because the Reality is created *randomly* at any measurement.

This eliminates the Realism in the Universe.

And, Bell's theorem and the experiments that followed it also actually states that the Universe is somehow connected via an immediate, yet not fully explained network, because a measurement *here* might influence something *there, immediately*, without any connection to the distance between *here and there*, or the velocity of Light.

This eliminates Locality in the Universe.

Thus, this debate started by an assumption that the Quantum Physics randomness is an illusion, and this debate was concluded by Bell's Theorem and Alain Aspect, John Clauser and Anton Zeilinger experiments, which presented that the Quantum Physics randomness is not an illusion, instead, the Space-Time notion might be considered as an illusion, because the Locality in the Universe seem to be an illusion.

And the above is also supported by the fact that Qubits, in modern Quantum Computers, exhibit the Quantum superposition phenomenon which implies that a single particle can be literally in *two different Locations at the same Time*.

And from the above presented Quantum Physics views, many physicists believe that Space doesn't actually exists in its own. They argue that Space is emergent, meaning it's a high-level "illusion", created by the way Quantum particles are linked (entangled) with each other.

Thus, if there were no particles and no relationships between them, then, there would be no "Space".

2. An alternate view of the Space-Time Nature might propose an alternate Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe

Despite the fact that in the nowadays Science of Classic Physics Einstein's Relativity theories are the leading acceptable theories of the Classic Physics, in several additional papers, by the author of this paper, significant and reasonable arguments were presented, which argue that the nowadays branch of the Classic Physics might be misleading in how it presents the concept of the Space-Time.

By presenting an alternative view of how the Science of Physics should refer to the concept of the Space-Time, possible bridging between incompatible branches of the nowadays Science of Physics might be achieved, a resolution to the famous Grandmother Paradox might be presented, and a reinstating of the Human's perception of the Free choice as an appropriate perception, and not as an illusion, misleading perception, might be also provided.

One of the above-mentioned additional papers is the paper: "Implications if the Electric Field will be recognized as a form of Acceleration." (8).

Another additional paper is the paper: "Tentative Additional Explanations to Why Electric Charges Attract and Repel Each Other" (9).

The above-mentioned two additional papers, (8) and (9), also present how the alternative view of how the Science of Physics should refer to the concept of the Space-Time, might provide leads for bridging between the Gravity and the Electromagnetism, which are branches of the Classic Physics which are still not fully compatible. Details can be found in these above-mentioned additional papers (8) and (9).

Still another additional paper is the paper: "Space-Time Nature might be used to bridge between the Quantum and the Classic Physics" (10). This additional paper also presents how the alternative view of how the Science of Physics should refer to the concept of the Space-Time, might provide a lead for bridging between the Classic Physics and the Quantum Physics, which are also two branches of the nowadays Science of Physics, which are still not compatible. Details can be found in this above-mentioned paper (10) .

And, still another additional paper: "An alternate Resolution of the Famous Grandmother Paradox which might be also validated via a classic experiment" (11), presents how the alternative view of how the Science of Physics should refer to the concept of the Space-Time, might also resolve the famous Grandmother Paradox. Details can be found in this above-mentioned paper (11).

These additional papers also propose real and physical experiments, based *only* on the Classic Physics, which if implemented successfully, might provide validity to the alternative view of how the Science of Physics should refer to the concept of the Space-Time, proposed by these additional papers.

Actually, the experiment presented in the paper: "Implications if the Electric Field will be recognized as a form of Acceleration." (8) might also support the conclusion, that the Space-Time concept should *not be* viewed as a real existing entity in the Universe.

Instead, the Space-Time concept should be viewed only as attributes, or facets, attributed to forms of Energy, such that each Energy embeds its own attribute, or facet, of Space-Time.

For example, Einstein's four-dimensional Interwoven Space-Time should be viewed only as a facet or an attribute, attributed to the Energy embedded in the Gravitational Field, and the Energy embedded in the Electromagnetic Fields should be attributed to *separate* attributes of Space and Time, or, a separate attribute of a four-dimensional Interwoven Space-Time attribute, *separate, different and independent* from Einstein's four-dimensional Interwoven Space-Time attribute, attributed to the Energy embedded in Gravity.

The paper: "Space-Time Nature might be used to bridge between the Quantum and the Classic Physics" (10) also argues that the Quantum branch of Physics also implies that the concept of

"Space" might not be a real entity, because it might be viewed as being emergent from entanglements between particles.

And the above is also supported by the fact that Qubits, in modern Quantum Computers, exhibit the Quantum superposition phenomenon which implies that a single particle can be literally in *two different Locations at the same Time*.

And from the above presented Quantum Physics views, many physicists believe that Space doesn't actually exist in its own. They argue that Space is emergent, meaning it's a high-level "illusion", created by the way Quantum particles are linked (entangled) with each other.

Thus, if there were no particles and no relationships between them, then, there would be no "Space".

Thus, in the proposed Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe, each such Space-Time is not considered to be a real, existing entity in the Existence, it should be viewed just as a facet, or an attribute of forms of Energies, which Humans might need to attribute to forms of Energies only as a mathematical tool in order to explain, or calculate, values related to *Interactions between forms of Energies*, such as Velocities or Accelerations.

3. Bell's Theorem might be also used to support the proposed Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe

As already presented before in this paper, Bell's Theorem actually provided the logic and the mathematics which was the basis of experiments which proved that Einstein's "Block Universe" model of the Universe is not completely correct, because it presents the Quantum Physics randomness as an illusion, while Bell's Theorem and the experiments that followed it, proved that the Quantum Physics randomness is correct, and not an illusion, and instead, Einstein's Space-Time concept might be an illusion, because Bell's Theorem and the experiments that followed it proved that the Locality perception of the Universe, might be an illusion.

The above complies with what is proposed also by the proposed Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe, which was presented in the previous chapter of this paper, because also in that proposed Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe, each Space-Time is not assumed to be a real, existing entity in the Existence.

Thus, from the above follows, that the Bell's Theorem might be used to provide additional support, to that proposed Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe.

But, as was also already presented before in this paper, although the Bell's Theory and Alain Aspect, John Clauser and Anton Zeilinger experiments proved that the Quantum Mechanics randomness is correct, it might be still also needed to fully understand, what actually happens in experiments relating to entangled particles, which is what was tested in Alain Aspect, John Clauser and Anton Zeilinger experiments, because the phenomenon of the Wave Function Collapse is still a mysterious, not fully understood phenomenon.

And the proposed Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe might provide that required extra explanation.

The proposed Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe presents that each Energy (particle) has its own private Space-Time facet, or attribute, which *is not a real entity*, that really exists in the Existence, and is used by Humans only to explain and understand how *Energies Interact*.

However, because Bell's Theorem and the experiments that followed it already proved that in a scenario of entangled particles, the distance between the particles is not a relevant piece of data, because the entangled particles are actually a united, one, *single Quantum system* regardless of the distance between the particles, then, in a scenario of entangled particles it should be assumed that *both* entangled particles might have the *same* facet, or attribute, of Space-Time, or, in other words, *both* entangled particles might have the *same* probabilistic Wave Function.

Thus, the above might imply that when *each* of the entangled particles interact with the environment, the Wave Functions of *both* entangled particles perform a *joint Wave Function collapse*, because the entangled particles are actually a united, one, *single Quantum system* regardless of the distance between the particles, which might have the *same* facet, or attribute, of Space-Time, or, in other words, *both* entangled particles might have the *same* probabilistic Wave Function, and this should explain the results achieved when experiments on entangled particles are performed, relating to the fact that a measurement of one particle *immediately* determines the state of the other particle, even if the distance between them is huge.

Thus, the above implies that what was assumed, as a yet not fully explained network, which might exist in the Universe, because a measurement *here* might influence something *there*, *immediately*, without any connection to the distance between *here and there*, or the velocity of Light, might not be an unexplained network at all.

Instead, this might just be a *same* facet, or attribute, of Space-Time, which also might imply a *same* Wave Function, that entangled particles might have.

4. Summary and Conclusions

This paper refers to additional papers, by the author of this paper, which present significant and reasonable arguments, which argue that the nowadays branch of the Classic Physics might be misleading in how it presents the concept of the Space-Time, and, these additional papers also propose an alternative possibility of how the concept of the Space-Time should be perceived, and also real, physical experiments, based *only* on the Classic Physics, which if implemented successfully, might also provide validity to the above-mentioned alternative possibility of how the concept of the Space-Time should be perceived.

This alternative possibility of how the concept of the Space-Time should be perceived propose, that the Einstein's Universe model, as a real, single Interwoven Space-Time should be replaced with a model of a Multi-Space-Times, where each such Space-Time is attributed to a different Energy, which also implies, that each of these Multi-Space-Times should not be considered to be a real, existing entity in the Existence, instead, each of these Multi-Space-Times should be viewed only as a facet, or an attribute, of the Energy which embeds this specific Space-Time.

This paper also provides reasonable arguments, that the Bell's Theorem might be also used to support the proposed model of the Multi-Space-Times of the Universe.

In addition to the above, this paper presents, that although Bell's Theorem and the experiments that followed it, did prove that the Quantum Physics randomness is correct, an additional explanation might be still required about what actually happens in experiments on entangled particles, relating to the fact that a measurement of one particle *immediately* determines the state of the other particle, even if the distance between them is huge.

This additional explanation seems to be still required because the "Wave Function Collapse" is still a mysterious, and not a fully understood phenomenon, and, this paper argues that the proposed model of the Multi-Space-Times might also provide this required additional explanation.

And because the alternative possibility of how the concept of the Space-Time should be perceived, proposed in this paper, do present leads for resolving incompatibilities between Physics branches, a significant resolution for the Grandmother Paradox, and a reinstating of the Human's perception of the Free Choice as an appropriate perception, then, in addition to the support that Bell's Theorem and the experiments that followed it might provide to the proposed Multi-Space-Times of the Universe, it might be also important to try and implement the additional experiments, referenced in the additional papers, which might provide additional validity to the Multi-Space-Times model of the Universe.

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